

Academic Procrastination And Metacognitive Strategies Among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University Students

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Abstract

The aim is to investigate the correlation between academic procrastination and metacognitive strategies among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students. This research study is quantitative and descriptive, based on the relationship between metacognition strategies and academic procrastination among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students. Participants were 350 Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students (females, $n=130$.37.1%, and males 220, 62.9%). The survey data were analyzed in SPSS (v. 22.0). The data were analyzed with Pearson correlation, and t-test. Findings indicated that the percentage of students who procrastinate their academic work is high, compared to individuals who do not repeat their work. Males procrastinate more than females. There are no statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to age. There are statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to college. Humanities colleges students procrastinate more than Scientific colleges students. There are significant correlations between all the study variables ($P < 0.01$).

Keywords: Academic procrastination ,metacognitive strategies ,Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University, students

Introduction

It cannot be said that the individual sometimes does not postpone some important work until a later time, especially in light of the technological and social changes (Demir& İlhan,2022) that have imposed themselves on individuals in various fields, which made time pass quickly(Kader & Eissa,2015 b) and created many life variables that some consider enjoyable. If it becomes a dominant feature of the personality of the individual (Kader& Eissa,2015 a), then it is considered a real problem that negatively affects the life of the individual because it affects his productivity and efficiency in facing the requirements of

daily life in various fields, and this is known as procrastination(Eissa& Gamal,2020; Mostafa, 2018).

Procrastination is defined as postponing tasks that should be completed at the present time for later fear of failure, wanting to avoid activities, promising to do them late, using excuses to justify procrastination and avoiding self-blame (Dugyala& Poyrazli, 2021) to result in subjective discomfort (Mohammed , Sherit& Eissa,2013).

It is also seen as the tendency of the individual to always or often postpone academic tasks, and always or often experience anxiety problems associated with this procrastination, and it is also

known as the obstruction or postponement of academic work that must be accomplished, and it seems that there are determinants of this behavior are: impeded productivity, unjustified, and unreasonably postpone tasks (Mahmoud , 2015;Uzun Özer& Sarıcaoğlu,2014).

Thus, it can be said that procrastination is characterized by delay, anxiety, productivity, and irrationality. Procrastination has become the center of many social problems, from the environment to health, as individuals put their fears aside and allow them to grow with time. Through the research, it was found that there are five different types of procrastination: decision-making procrastination, neurotic procrastination, compulsive procrastination, procrastination in routine daily life, and academic procrastination (Goroshit& Hen,2021; Yalın& Özlem,2022).

Academic procrastination has many negative consequences for students, such as: psychological stress, anxiety, feelings of conflict and guilt, health problems, lack of productivity and social rejection; Failure to fulfill social obligations and responsibilities. The procrastinator suffers from not obtaining support for it. It has become known as laziness and weak ambition (Steel, 2007), and academic procrastination has been linked to poor achievement(Yalın& Özlem,2022), absenteeism (Koppenborg & Klingsieck,2022), and it is a weak point in personality that leads to a decrease in self-confidence (Asude & Aynur,2018).

By reviewing the literature on the causes of procrastination, it was found that the two most frequent causes of procrastination are: unpleasant and boring tasks (Rashmi & Sampreety,2021). Procrastinators avoid working under pressure and prefer to work with tasks that bring pleasure to them, and these

individuals have no future orientation, and a lack of self-esteem and self-efficacy(Asude & Aynur,2018). Therefore, in order to protect themselves, they put off work that they think they may fail in, and some of the causes of academic procrastination are: fear of failure, teacher style, alienating task, risk taking, resistance to control, and peer pressure (Abdi Zarrin, & Gracia,2020).

It can be said that the imbalance in metacognitive strategies may fall among these reasons because the dysfunction of these strategies may cause stereotypical thinking style, maladaptive routine attention, and behavioral dysfunction in the form of attention-cognitive syndrome. It has been shown that cognitive self-awareness strategies facilitate adaptive patterns in case of anxiety and compulsive action (ElAdl, & Polpol,2020; Khalik,2014).

Metacognitive strategies include: the individual's knowledge of his cognitive processes and production and any of the matters associated with them such as: characteristics of relevant learning information, effective monitoring, organization, sequential control and coordination, to achieve influence on cognitive processes to serve certain goals (Eissa,2015).

These strategies include the following: Self-directing, in which the individual decides whether he has sufficient information to do what is required, Self-monitoring, in which the individual performs the action and behavior that he has chosen, and follows the steps he wanted to do self-evaluating in which the individual decides if the work he does leads to the desired (Gomaa,2016), self-correcting and in which the individual, through the information available to him about his behavior and the desired result, corrects his course of action to reach this

result (Demir& İlhan,2022), self-control, which refers to the individual's control and control of his behavior based on the outcomes of the previous strategies (Özer,2021), and following the appropriate behavior to reach the goal, the individual in these strategies is a thinker and a self-organizer, so that he takes responsibility for his behavior using metacognitive strategies to identify problems, especially when these problems are not solved with his previous knowledge, and he also monitors and evaluates time, energy and ideas, to choose the appropriate behavior for the situation (Huseini,2015).

Aims

The aim is to investigate the correlation between academic procrastination and metacognitive strategies among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students.

Research questions

Core Question: What is the correlation between academic procrastination and metacognitive strategies among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students?

Sub-Questions

1. What is the prevalence of academic procrastination among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students?
2. Are there statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to gender, age and college variables?
3. Is there a statistically significant relationship between metacognition strategies and academic procrastination among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students?

Research Design

This research study is quantitative and descriptive, based on the relationship between metacognition strategies and

academic procrastination among Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students.

Sample

A convenience sampling method was used to recruit Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students in this study. The inclusion criteria were as follows: a) Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students, b) both sexes (males and Females), c) from Scientific colleges and humanities colleges, and d) Students of class groups from one to four. Participants were 350 Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students (females, n= 130 .37.1%, and males 220, 62.9%). Subjects participated on a voluntary basis. Informed and written consent was obtained from all participants.

Instruments

Academic Procrastination Scale (Kader& Eissa,2015). A 25- item survey instrument , intended to assess academic procrastination among college students. The response method was a Likert 5-point scale. The higher the score, the greater the procrastination degree is. The Test-retest coefficient reported by Kader& Eissa (2015) was 0.89. The scale was validated using 86 undergraduates consisting of diverse academic majors and years of college completion.

Metacognitive Strategies Scale. A 50- item survey instrument was developed particularly for this research study. The first part concerns with the demographic information, while the second parts concerns with scale items for the five subscales: self- directing, self- monitoring, self control, self-evaluating, and self-correcting. The coefficients of internal consistency of the subscales ranged from 0.85 to 0.91 .

Discriminant validity test using Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity was strongly significant ($P < 0.001$), indicating the great suitability of this instrument for validity estimate.

Data Analysis

The survey data were analyzed in SPSS (v. 22.0). The data were analyzed with Pearson correlation, and t-test.

Results

To answer the first question of the study, "What is the prevalence of academic procrastination among Bin Abdulaziz University students?" ,the percentage of individuals who scored less than (75) was calculated, that is, students with low procrastination, and their percentage in relation to the sample was 33.6%, while the percentage of students who got a score of (75) or more was 35.7% ,which means the prevalence of academic procrastination among Bin Abdulaziz University students. This result is consistent with the results of

previous studies (e.g. Solomon & Rothblum,1984, Steel,2007, Balks & Duru,2009; Hayat ,Jahanian, Bazrafcan &Shokrpour,2020) .Those authors indicated that the percentage of students who procrastinate their academic work is high, compared to individuals who do not repeat their work.

To answer the second question " Are there statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to gender, age and college variables? ", t-test was used, as shown in tables 1-3. Table 1 shows that (t) value was (6.21, $P < 0.01$) , that is , males procrastinate more than females . Table 2 shows that (t) value was (0.867, $P=0.632$) , that is , there are no statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to age. Table 3 shows that (t) value was (5.324, $P < 0.01$) , that is , there are statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to college. Humanities colleges students procrastinate more than Scientific colleges students.

Table 1 academic procrastination due to gender

Group	N	Mean	Std. deviation	T	P
Females	130	59.25	1.02	6.21	0.01
Males	220	71.86	3.12		

Table 2 academic procrastination due to age

Group	N	Mean	Std. deviation	T	P
91-20	180	64.11	2.04	0.867	0.632
21-23	170	61.80	3.15		

Table 3 academic procrastination due to college

Group	N	Mean	Std. deviation	T	P
Scientific colleges	190	58.17	1.55	5.324	0.01
humanities	160	67.85	1.74		

 colleges

Inter-correlations

Table 4 shows the means, inter-correlations of self-directing, self-monitoring, self control, self-evaluating,

self-correcting, and academic procrastination . Table 4 shows that there are significant correlations between all the study variables ($P < 0.01$).

Table 4 Inter-correlations of study variables

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1.Academic procrastination						
2.Self- directing	-.622**					
3.Self- monitoring	-.611**					
4.Self- control	-.642**					
5.Self- evaluating	-.633**					
6. Self- correcting	-.612**					

Discussion

Based on the results, The percentage of individuals who scored less than (75) was calculated, that is, students with low procrastination, and their percentage in relation to the sample was 33.6%, while the percentage of students who got a score of (75) or more was 35.7% ,which means the prevalence of academic procrastination among Bin Abdulaziz University students. This may be due to the fact that many students who procrastinate consider academic tasks unpleasant, increase their feelings of anxiety, and are afraid of failing in them; their low self-esteem and lack of self-efficacy in these tasks, peer pressure plays a role in procrastination processes, and the future tendency to benefit from their academic majors in their future lives appears to be little; because many graduates may work in jobs that differ from these disciplines, and the technological changes that have occurred in the processes of communication with others can be added to the above, which

many students consider interesting tasks and spend a long time in them; this is because it has become available in every place and time, for all this they procrastinate their academic work.

As shown in table 1 , it can be noted that there are statistically significant differences in the students' performance on the academic procrastination scale due to the gender variable. T-value was (6.21, $P < 0.01$) , that is , males procrastinate more than females. This result is consistent with that by Kahn et al.(2014) , but differs with the result of Ozer & Ferrari(2009) who found that there is no a statistically significant difference between males and females in academic procrastination. The reason may be that there are statistically significant differences in academic procrastination in favor of males; That is, they delay their academic work more than females because of the nature and importance of university studies for females through which they want to prove their worth and entitlement at the

university, and then in practical life. As for males, they do not have enough motivation to study, especially in the absence of job opportunities in the market for specializations. academics, which leads to their weak orientation towards academic work.

As shown in table 2 , T-value was (0.867,P=0.632) , that is , there are statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to age. This result differs with the result of that of Kahn, et al.(2014), which indicated that procrastination decreases with age, but it is similar to the result of the study (Cao, 2012), which indicated that both adult students procrastinate, but the difference between them is in the type of procrastination, where youngsters practice active procrastination while adults practice passive procrastination.

This is because a high percentage of the current study sample ranges in age from 21-23 years, in other words, they belong to the same age group, which is the beginnings of early adulthood, and this means that they have the same academic and professional orientations, so the current study did not find significant differences attributed to the age variable. As for the study of Kahn, et al. (2014), its sample consisted of individuals aged between (16-27), meaning that they belong to two different stages: adolescence and early adulthood, which led to significant differences attributed to the age variable, as younger individuals are more procrastinating than older individuals, and the reason for the study to reach this result may be that it used the academic procrastination scale in general, whose paragraphs contain active procrastination and passive procrastination, and the current study did not test this difference. Therefore, no statistically significant differences were found in academic

procrastination attributable to the age variable.

Table 3 shows that (t) value was (5.324, $P < 0.01$) , that is , there are statistically significant differences in academic procrastination due to college. Humanities colleges students procrastinate more than Scientific colleges students. This means that academic procrastination increases among students of humanities colleges, and this result is in agreement to some extent with the result of Kahn, et al.(2014), who indicated that college students procrastinate more than university students, and he explained the result by the nature of university studies, which requires effort and serious work compared to studying in colleges, and this applies to me the difference between the nature of study in scientific colleges and humanities colleges, where courses in scientific colleges focus on the practical side and projects, while courses in humanities colleges focus on the theoretical side and studying in scientific colleges requires serious work and organized time, to fulfill the requirements of studying in these faculties, so students in humanities faculties may procrastinate their work more than students of scientific faculties because they can achieve them in the last moments.

Table 4 shows the means, inter-correlations of self- directing, self-monitoring, self control, self-evaluating, self-correcting, and academic procrastination . Table 4 shows that there are significant correlations between all the study variables ($P < 0.01$). There is a negative relationship between metacognitive strategies and academic procrastination, meaning that students who possess these strategies in a high degree have less academic procrastination than students who possess these strategies with a low degree, and this is consistent with

what was indicated by Flavel (1976) that these strategies refer to: knowing the characteristics of relevant learning information, effective monitoring, organization, sequential control and coordination, and all of these strategies make the individual able to face different situations and be organized; So that he can achieve his goals on time, within a well-thought-out plan, and make him able to follow his mental processes while performing tasks, and allow him to review and adjust them, which leads to less delay in his academic work.

Conclusion

The study has garnered crucial observations with regard to student behaviour in handling academic tasks. The likelihood to procrastinate was found to be higher for males, compared to females. There is a negative relationship between metacognitive strategies and academic procrastination, meaning that students who possess these strategies in a high degree have less academic procrastination than students who possess these strategies with a low degree.

Limitations

In the present research, we used a self-report questionnaires, which might have involved some bias. Moreover, the data were collected from the medical students studying at Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University students; this limits the generalizability of the results to the students of other universities and other majors. Also, this was a cross-sectional research study in which the data were collected in a specific time period. Therefore, it is suggested that further research be carried out longitudinally to determine the level of procrastination behaviors among the students.

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